

MARINE PARKS AS A DESTINATION CHOICE OF MILLENNIAL TOURISTS: THE ROLE OF CONSUMPTION VALUES AND RESPONSIBLE ENVIRONMENTAL BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract: Marine parks are popular ecotourism holiday destinations besides being an important conservational zone for the marine life. The sustainability of marine parks is highly dependent on the visitors' behaviour, especially millennials who are an imperative tourist segment that are implied to be supportive of the green movement. Personal consumption values have yet to be widely used to predict tourists' environmental behaviour and especially on their destination decision. Furthermore, there have been contradicting findings between the tourists' consumption values and their environmental behaviour when visiting ecotourism destinations. Thus, the purpose of this study is to examine the influence of personal consumption values on responsible environmental behaviour, and the mediating effect of responsible environmental behaviour between these values and their destination choice. A face to face survey was conducted among 409 local and international millennial tourists at the top three marine parks in Malaysia using purposive sampling. The data was analysed using partial least squares structural equation modelling method to determine the relationships between the tourists' consumption values, responsible environmental behaviour and destination choice. The result of this study confirms that personal consumption values did have a significant but weak influence on tourists' pro environmental behaviours. It further confirms that millennial tourists who are environmentally responsible prefers to visit marine park islands as their holiday destination. This study highlights the importance of attracting the right tourist segment to promote ecotourism destinations.

Keywords: Consumption Values, Destination Choice, Ecotourism, Marine Parks, Responsible Environmental Behaviour, Sustainability

Introduction

Over the years, there has been a widespread of growing support for ecotourism, instead of mass tourism due to the growing concern for global environmental issues. Malaysia has been identified as one of the popular ecotourism destination in its region due to its tropical weather and abundant flora and fauna (United Nations World Tourism Organization 2019). The marine park islands are one of the famous sites in Malaysia for ecotourism among the local and foreign tourists and most of the marine park islands in Malaysia are located in Terengganu, Johor, Pahang, and Sabah (Department of Marine Park Malaysia 2017).

One of the key contributor that have helped shape ecotourism is the millennial tourist segment. Based on majority of definitions, millennials are those born between the years of 1980 to 2000 (Cavagnaro and Staffieri, 2015). According to the United Nations, millennial tourists generate more than \$180 billion in annual tourism revenue and is expected to reach \$340 billion by 2020 (Oxford Economics, 2010) and about 58 percent of global millennials live in Asia (AT Kearney, 2018). As the generation moves up the purchasing power pyramid overtaking its predecessors the baby boomers, millennials have taken center stage for marketers and researchers alike.

Millennial tourists have a significant influence on the tourism sector. They love to travel to novel destinations where they can immerse themselves in local and unique experiences. This generation prefers to spend their extra money on vacations rather than buying a new car.

However, the millennials are not to be mistaken as careless or carefree. They are savvy tourists that are well-exposed and highly connected to the world through social media and mobile applications. Information on travel destinations and choices are just at the tip of their fingers. Besides, they view travelling as a need, not a luxury, as it is deemed important for their personal growth and overall well-being. In this notion, their consumption patterns and decision-making process may differ from the typical tourist.

Generally, studies related to pro-environmental behaviour is not a new phenomenon but findings from these studies have been elusive. There exists a preconception that ecotourists are more aware about the dire environmental situation and would want to contribute by behaving more responsibly. Furthermore, most of the studies concentrated on understanding the antecedents of behaviour intention in general, without exploring its' effect on certain specific decisions (Zhang et al., 2014). Past studies have examined consumers' purchasing behaviour towards green products such as cars, household products, and green food (Vermeir and Verbeke, 2008; McDonald et al., 2009; Oliver and Lee, 2010; Young et al., 2010; Mohd Suki and Mohd Suki, 2015b) . Despite the various studies conducted on pro-environmental behaviour, most studies found that there is a disconnection between their perception towards green practices and their willingness to take action (Line and Hanks, 2016). Consumers have been said to make different choices in different environmental situation or context. In pursuit of responsible consumerism, it is not uncommon to see tourists place more emphasis on cost and comfort over environmental cause. Indeed, there is still much to uncover about their consumption behaviours and choices.

Thus, it is hoped that the findings of this study would fill the knowledge gaps on responsible millennial tourists' behaviour and their destination choice. Subsequently, this study provides empirical evidence to identify the motivation and preferences of this segment to support the sustainability of the natural resources in the marine park islands.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Tourists' Responsible Environmental Behaviour and Destination Choice

Tourists' behaviour is a thriving field of study that is vital to the development and sustainability of the tourism industry. Numerous studies have been conducted to understand the overall tourists' behavior focusing on their satisfaction, visit intention, travelling decisions. In hospitality sector, studies have focused on understanding tourists' intention towards staying in green hotels (Han and Kim, 2010; Chen and Tung, 2014; Mohd Suki and Mohd Suki, 2015a) and specific activities such as recycling and energy-saving (Bezzina and Dimech, 2011; Gadenne et al., 2011; Saripah and Mohd Shukri, 2012; Ramayah and Rahbar, 2013).

Tourists' pro-environmental behavior is constantly evolving in view of the influences from the external environmental such as technological advancements, climate change issues and globalization. In explaining tourists behavior, a simple linear model linking knowledge, attitude and behavior was proposed in the early 70s (Lu and Wang, 2018). In view of the increasingly challenging global environmental issues, further studies introduced expanded models and additional dimensions of attitude and social norm as predictors in the 1980s. Two such popular models that were developed and repeatedly tested were the theory of reasoned action (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980) and the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1985). Nonetheless, these rational-choice theories insufficiently explain environmentally-friendly behaviors,—while attitude was often found to be a poor predictor of behaviours, as people often make choices based on their personal values (Weeden, 2014).

Environmentally responsible tourists have also been referred to as ecotourists, ethical tourists, green tourists and sustainable tourists. However, Weeden (2008) questions if responsible consumers and ecotourists are even coincidentally same or different from each other. Tourists are often not homogenous and wish to fulfil different needs when choosing a destination over another. For example, ecotourists are those who are more inclined towards nature-based destinations, preferring nature parks compared to man-made settings. They also prefer destinations that offer adventurous outdoor activities that do not disrupt the ecosystem such as bird - watching and hiking. In a study by Kelly et al., (2007), ecotourists supported destinations that practiced eco-friendly options that they perceive would help to offset the negative impacts of their visits.

Holiday destination choices involve various considerations and often highly bounded by the context, may evolve over time and are often difficult to fully understand (Decrop and Snelders, 2004). Early studies on destination choice posited that tourists are rational and thus go through a logical decision-making process whereby consumers buy to achieve optimum worth or utility in exchange of the price paid (Moutinho, 1987). Therefore, past studies on destination choice have focused on price, distance and cost (Nicolau and Más, 2006). Besides, tourists' perception towards the overall quality of the natural environment have also been found to be a significant predictor of destination choice (Mihalič, 2000). Over the years, the growth of services sector has forced researchers and marketers too look at tourism differently compared to purchasing process of products. Gilbert (1991) advocates that decision making model should emphasize on behaviour as functional concept, and further looks into the effect of that decision on future behaviours. Furthermore, the bibliographic study by Saito and Strehlau (2018) concluded that various psychological and social aspects exists in understanding destination decision making process. Meyer (1988) suggested that tourists' travelling decisions are a form of an escape from everyday life to seek rich life experiences. Furthermore, tourists travel for many reasons such as to unwind, relax or to spend quality time with their family and friends, often above and beyond their commitments to the nature. For some of the tourists, they may act more responsibly if their overall vacation experience is not compromised and certain incentives were provided in return.

2.2 Personal Consumption Values

A tourist's behaviour and decisions may differ as tourism products are experiential, intangible and heterogeneous. As such, consumption values have been said to a good predictor of responsible tourists' behaviours (Gatersleben et al., 2014). Personal consumption patterns and lifestyle changes are important factors that would influence behaviour and decisions. The potential influence of consumption values on consumer choice was emphasized in Sheth et al., (1991) consumption values theory. Consumers are said to be influence by functionality, social identity, emotionality, uniqueness and other conditions respectively.

Sheth et al., (1991) described personal consumption values as multidimensional drivers of consumer choice. Consumption values have previously been tested in relation to destination image (Ramkissoon et al., 2009), destination choice (Phau et al., 2014) and post-visit behaviour such as loyalty (Wan et al., 2018) but its influence on responsible environmental behaviour has yet to be attempted. The functional value represents the monetary and overall worth of consuming the vacation services. Functional value is often evaluated from the visitors' perception towards the overall quality and economical price of their holiday. Functional value has been established to be a strong predictor towards behaviour intention and destination decision (Wang et al., 2018).

Whereas emotional value is the feelings of happiness and joy from consuming the products or services. Emotional value was found to have the most influence on destination decision (Denys

and Mendes, 2014). When consuming tourism and leisure services, tourists desire to satisfy their emotional experiences (Brunner-Sperdin et al., 2012). Studies have found that Malaysians are motivated to travel for pleasure to natural sites (Norzalita and Ahmad, 2009). Thus, recreation experience in nature-based destinations allows tourists' emotions to be aroused and result in more pro-environmental practices.

Epistemic value, on the other hand, is the importance of uniqueness and novelty that the consumer experience. Based on a study conducted on Chinese students, epistemic value was an important determinant of green products' purchase intention as it made them feel special using the products (Ma et al., 2018). Epistemic value turned out to be the most prominent dimension by contributing the highest weightage among the overall consumption values and had a significant positive impact on sustainable consumption behaviour (Burcu and Seda, 2013; Biswas and Roy, 2015). For a traveller, the epistemic value may be achieved through participation in local socio-cultural activities that is unique to the destination. For example, in a study conducted among local and international tourists' perception, both groups indicated high importance on Thailand as an exotic holiday destination with regards to its cultural heritage and natural environment (Henkel et al., 2006).

Additionally, social norms is one of the key antecedents of consumer decision and therefore a vital concept in this study. Consumers' self-identity becomes increasingly important in defining how they view themselves in relation to the community. A responsible tourist may develop stronger social value if they perceive that their pro-environmental behaviours would allow them to be associated to some social groups. In a study by Biswas and Roy (2014) on green products in the context of the emerging market of India, they found that social values play a significant role in sustainable consumption behaviours.

Consequently, it may not seem possible for ecotourists to make responsible consumption choices all the time. Just like any other consumers, responsible tourists may face certain trade-offs in view of their holiday choices. As such, conditional values measure their perceived utility towards a certain situational context. For example, a tourist would be more inclined to act responsibly if he or she are more aware about the deteriorating environmental conditions such as pollution.

Consumption values have been confirmed to influence tourists' loyalty towards the destination (Wan et al., 2018), however limited studies were found specifically on linking consumption values to ecotourists' responsible behaviour and their preference towards marine park islands specifically. Tourists' involvement has been said to play the role of partial mediators towards sustainable behaviours (Chiu et al., 2013). Concurrently, higher levels of involvement and participation in the tourism recreation activities strengthens their values and increases the well-being of their overall experience in responsible environmental behaviours (Hung and Jan, 2015; Mathis et al., 2016).

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Framework

Below Figure 1 depicts the research framework underlying this study. Based on the review of the various past literatures, it is hypothesized that personal consumption values as theorized by Sheth et al., (1991) is a formative construct consisting of functional, social, emotional, epistemic and conditional values. It is hypothesized that personal consumption values has a positive and significant relationship towards responsible environmental behaviour of tourists, and responsible environmental behaviour has a positive influence on their destination choice. It is further postulated that this variable also acts as mediator between personal consumption values and destination choice.

Figure 1: Research Framework

3.2 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The sample population for this study was local and international tourists who have recently visited any one of the top three marine park islands located in Malaysia, namely Perhentian, Tioman and Redang islands. A purposive sampling technique was used whereby only millennial tourists aged between 18 and 38 years were targeted. Based on G*power calculator, the sample size of 92 is considered sufficient with medium effect size ($f^2=0.15$), α level of 0.05 and power of 0.80 (Gefen, et al., 2000). A total of 500 survey questions were distributed to ensure high response rate.

3.3 Data Collection Methods

The paper-based questionnaires were distributed via face-to-face method to local and international tourists arriving at the jetties from the three marine park islands. Filtering questions were asked before the survey were handed out to ensure that respondents were amongst the millennial age group and have recently visited the marine park islands. The researchers were present on-site to oversee and assist the respondents in completing the questionnaires. The data was collected over the period of 4 months (March – June 2019). Overall, a total of 409 usable questionnaires were returned, which yielded a response rate of 81.8%.

3.4 Questionnaire Design

Based on the respondents' personal language preferences, they had a choice to answer the survey in English, Malay or Chinese language. Before the final questionnaires were distributed, a pre-test was conducted among panel experts consisting of tour guides and academicians. Some minor improvements such as the wordings in the questionnaire were changed to improve the clarity of the statements. The final questionnaire consisted of three parts whereby the first part had 22 questions measuring the five dimensions of consumption values that was adapted from Sweeney and Soutar (2001) and Phau et al., (2014). These questions were measured on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 for "strongly disagree" to 7 for "strongly agree". In the second part of the survey, a total of 7 questions were asked to measure responsible environment behaviour (REB) and 3 questions on destination choice. The questions on REB were adapted from Chiu et al., (2014) whereas items measuring destination choice were adapted from Lam

and Hsu (2006). For this part, all the 10 items were measured on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 for “strongly disagree” to 5 for “strongly agree”. As all the measurement items were adapted for this study, the scales were maintained accordingly as used in the previous studies. More importantly, the usage of different scale endpoints helps to reduce common method biases caused by commonalities in scale endpoints (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The last part of the questionnaire consisted of questions on demographic characteristics and their recent travel patterns to the marine park island.

3.5 Data Analysis

The descriptive data was analysed using SPSS Ver. 22 and the partial least squares-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) technique was applied using Smart PLS Ver 3.0 software to further test the pre-conceived model. Considered as the second-generation multivariate technique, the PLS-SEM was conducted using a two-stage approach whereby the measurement model was first evaluated to determine the reliability and validity of the indicators towards the constructs. This is followed by examining the structural model to test the hypotheses by using a bootstrapping method (500 resamples) as prescribed by Hair et al. (2017). As the model consisted of a formative construct - Personal Consumption Values (PCV), a global indicator item was included in the questionnaire to enable the researchers to conduct the higher order construct analysis (Mackenzie et al. 2011).

The common method variance needed to be addressed as this study used a self-reported measures from the same sample that may cause some bias or systematic error (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Tehseen et al., 2017). As such, the Harman’s single-factor test was conducted to remedy this as it is viewed as the most common method (Sharma et al., 2009). All items were loaded into a factor analysis in SPSS and the results indicated that the total variance explained was 79.5% and the restricted extraction of a single factor only explained 48.4% of the variance, thus inferring that the data did not have any prevalent common method issue.

4 Findings

4.1 Demographic Profile

Referring to Table 1, out of the total 409 respondents, there were 53.8% female respondents and 46.2% male respondents, considerably quite a balanced distribution of genders. The majority of the respondents were Malaysian tourists (63.8%), followed by Singapore (6.8%) and China (6.6%) tourists. Overall, the total foreign tourists who participated in the survey was 36.2%. This distribution was considered favourable as the distribution of tourists to all the marine park islands in Malaysia based on 2016 data was 60% local and 40% foreign tourists (Department of Marine Park Malaysia, 2017). In terms of age distribution, most of them were between the age of 23 to 27 years old (30.6%). With regards to their travelling patterns, 64.3% of them stayed for less than a week and a total of 54% of them travelled with their family. As for their choice of accommodation, 57.9% stayed in a hotel or resort. All the respondents have indicated that they have recently visited one of the marine park islands with Tioman Island having the most visit amongst them respondents.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Profile	Categories	Frequency	%	Profile	Categories	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	189	46.2	Age	18-22	102	24.9
	Female	220	53.8		23-27	125	30.6
Nationality	Malaysia	261	63.8		28-32	85	20.8
	Australia	3	0.7		33-38	97	23.7
	Bangladesh	2	0.5	Length of stay	< 1 week	263	64.3
	Britain	4	1.0		1 week	73	17.8
	Cambodia	1	0.2		1-2 weeks	26	6.4
	China	27	6.6		2-4 weeks	21	5.1
	France	14	3.4	> 1 month	26	6.4	
	Germany	5	1.2	Travel company	Alone	45	11.0
	India	2	0.5		With family	221	54.0
	Indonesia	8	2.0		With friend(s)	143	35.0
	Iran	4	1.0	Accommodation	Hotel/Resort	237	57.9
	Italy	2	0.5		Apartment	30	7.3
	Japan	5	1.2		Hostel	46	11.2
	Lithuania	1	0.2		Homestay	78	19.1
	Malta	1	0.2	Others	18	4.4	
	Netherlands	3	0.7	Marine Park Island Visited	Tioman	217	53.1
	New Zealand	4	1.0		Redang	159	38.9
	Philippines	10	2.4		Perhentian	153	37.4
	Poland	4	1.0				
	Republic of Korea	4	1.0				
Singapore	28	6.8					
Sudan	1	0.2					
Syria	1	0.2					
Ukraine	1	0.2					
Tanzania	2	0.5					
Thailand	1	0.2					
USA	6	1.5					
Vietnam	3	0.7					
Yemen	1	0.2					

4.2 Measurement Model Assessments

4.2.1 Convergent Validity

First, the convergent validity and the discriminant validity is assessed in the measurement model provided in Figure 2. The measurements items are considered acceptable if the standardized loading values are more than 0.7; Cronbach's alpha are greater than 0.708; CR values are greater than 0.8 and AVE values are more than 0.5 (Hair et al., 2010). The results of factor loadings, composite reliability (CR), Cronbach's alpha and average variance extracted (AVE) of all the measurement items for the first order constructs are summarized in Table 2. Results indicate that only the loadings for REB6a (0.617), REB6e (0.676) and REB6g (0.690) were all slightly below 0.70, however as the CR (0.89) and AVE (0.537) values met the minimum thresholds, these items were maintained. All other measurement items satisfied the requirements and met the convergent validity suggesting that items are reliable and valid (Hair et al., 2014).

To evaluate the formative measures, a redundancy analysis is conducted to determine its convergent validity by creating a new path model drawn separately to predict the single measurement item. As depicted in Table 2, the formative construct of Personal Consumption Values' path coefficient is 0.858; above the recommended threshold of 0.70, indicating that the overall construct has sufficient convergent validity (Ramayah et al., 2018). Additionally, the collinearity among the formative items of the construct were determined by inspecting the value of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Table 2 shows that the VIF values for the five consumption values dimensions range between 2.32 and 7.273. The scores are less than 10,

confirming that no critical multi-collinearity exists among the constructs and all items are retained (Hair et al, 2010).

Next, the significance of outer weights for the formative measurement items were determined by conducting a bootstrapping of 500 resamples. Table 2 reveals that the formative indicators of emotional, epistemic and conditional values are found to be significant (t -value > 1.645), except for social value and functional value. However, the consumption values theory by Sheth et al., (1991) and other past studies (see Ladhari and Tchetgna, 2014; Biswas and Roy, 2015) have provided evidence that both the indicators of social value and functional value dimensions are relevant and thus, both are retained in this study.

Figure 2: Assessment of Measurement Model

Table 2: Measurement Model Results

First-order Construct	Second-order Construct	Item	Scale	Loading s/ Weights	CR/ t-values	Cronbach Alpha	AVE/ VIF
Functional Value		FV3a	Reflective	0.833	0.948	0.931	0.785
		FV3b		0.894			
		FV3c		0.931			
		FV3d		0.896			
		FV3e		0.872			
Social Value		SV3f	Reflective	0.938	0.959	0.943	0.855
		SV3g		0.903			
		SV3h		0.938			
		SV3i		0.919			
Emotional Value		EM3j	Reflective	0.930	0.964	0.951	0.871
		EM3k		0.936			
		EM3l		0.925			
		EM3m		0.942			
Epistemic Value		EP3n		0.924	0.970	0.962	0.867
		EP3o		0.938			
		EP3p		0.927			
		EP3q		0.945			
		EP3r		0.923			
Conditional Value		CO3s		0.809	0.924	0.891	0.753
		CO3t		0.857			
		CO3u		0.903			
		CO3v		0.898			
Responsible Env Beh		REB6a	Reflective	0.617	0.890	0.855	0.537
		REB6b		0.798			
		REB6c		0.766			
		REB6d		0.790			
		REB6e		0.676			
		REB6f		0.774			
		REB6g		0.690			
PCV Global item Destination Choice		SIM	SIM	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
		DC7a	Reflective	0.920	0.935	0.896	0.828
		DC7b		0.921			
		DC7c		0.887			
	<i>Personal Consumption Values</i>	Path Coefficient	0.858				
		<i>Functional Value</i>	<i>Formative</i>	0.028	0.495	N/A	2.320
		<i>Social Value</i>		-0.029	0.636		2.620
		<i>Emotional Value</i>		0.268	3.436*		7.273
		<i>Epistemic Value</i>		0.311	4.105*		6.791
		<i>Conditional Value</i>		0.346	5.582*		3.813

Note: AVE= Average Variance Extracted; CR = Composite Reliability; SIM = Single Item Measurement; Sig at t-values > 1.645*

4.2.2 Discriminant Validity

The measurement model's discriminant validity is then examined to determine whether the items are measuring different constructs and if each construct was statistically dissimilar to each other (Henseler et al., 2014). To confirm the discriminant validity, Table 3 depicts the results using the Fornell and Larcker Criterion. According to the results, the square root of the AVE (diagonals and bolded) are all above the values of the off-diagonal variances among constructs, thus establishing the discriminant validity. In this instance, there is no serious multicollinearity issue that exist among the measurement items for each construct.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Constructs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Conditional Value	0.868							
2. Emotional Value	0.829	0.933						
3. Epistemic Value	0.822	0.912	0.931					
4. Functional Value	0.704	0.699	0.721	0.886				
5. Destination Choice	0.167	0.164	0.156	0.304	0.910			
6. Personal Consumption Values	0.823	0.836	0.839	0.665	0.157	1		
7. Responsible Env Beh	0.295	0.279	0.247	0.336	0.538	0.273	0.733	
8. Social Value	0.716	0.766	0.733	0.636	0.155	0.670	0.204	0.925

4.3 Structural Model Assessment

Upon satisfying the measurement model's reliability and validity assessments, the structural model's path analysis is executed to confirm the relevant hypothesized relationships in this study. The estimated standardized beta coefficients of the structural model is examined to determine the strength of the relationship between the variables. Additionally, the coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates the amount of variance explained by the independent variables (Hair et al., 2014). Results of the structural model analysis are provided in **Table 4**.

The predictor of personal consumption values on responsible environmental behaviour was confirmed to be significantly positive ($\beta = 0.273$, $p < 0.05$). However, the R^2 value of 0.075 is considered weak, whereby indicating that only 7.5% of the variance in REB is explained by PCV. On the other hand, H2 is also supported whereby responsible environmental behaviour is also positively related to destination choice ($\beta = 0.538$, $p < 0.05$). The R^2 value of 0.290 is substantial as suggested by Cohen (1988) and this indicated that 29% of the variance in DC can be explained by REB.

The mediation hypothesis is tested using the bootstrapping technique. The results in **Table 4** shows that the relationship between PCV and DC is mediated by REB ($\beta = 0.147$, $p < 0.05$) are significant with t-value of 3.817. Thus, it can be concluded that the mediation effects of REB are statistically significant at t-value > 1.96 and p-value < 0.05 .

Table 4: Hypotheses Results

Hypothesis	Std Beta (β)	Std Error	t-value	p-value	R ²		Decision	
					LL	UL		
H1 PCV → REB	0.273	0.065	4.199	0.000	0.152	0.404	0.075	Supported**
H2 REB → DC	0.538	0.04	13.393	0.000	0.451	0.606	0.290	Supported**
H3 PCV → REB → DC	0.147	0.039	3.817*	0.000	0.077	0.229	-	Supported***

Note: **t-value > 1.645 , $p < 0.05$; ***t-value > 1.96 , $p < 0.05$

5. Discussions

This study posited that personal consumption values has a positive relationship towards responsible environmental behaviour. The empirical results of the present study confirm that millennial tourists' personal consumption values did have a positive influence on their responsible environmental behaviour. From this study, three dimensions of personal consumption values, which includes emotional value, epistemic value and conditional value contributed to their overall consumption values. Specifically, conditional value had the highest contribution, followed by epistemic value and emotional value towards the overall consumption values. Conditional value is perceived as a situational preference whereby tourists gives consideration to the current environmental situation or in the case of being offered with some sort of an incentive. This includes the facilitation provided by the marine park management that eases them or the worsening condition of the parks urging them to behave more responsibly. These conditions act as a pull factor that motivates and attract tourists to behave more responsibly. However, in comparison to urban destinations, tangible and intangible incentives were found to have no influence on tourists' willingness to participate in conservational programs especially in nature-based destinations (Line, Hanks and Miao, 2017).

Furthermore, epistemic values refer to the tourists' feelings of excitement when they are experiencing something different or unique at the marine park islands. This is in view that marine park islands acted as an escapism for them and visiting the islands made them feel more pleasurable. Positive emotional values are feelings of happiness and relaxation that arises from the tourists' evaluation of their travel experience. More distinctly, a pleasant activation of their emotions would increase their overall consumption experience and result in a positive evaluation. Although tourists were said to enjoy the utilitarian benefits of a holiday, they have been found to place more importance on the hedonic benefits (Chandon et al., 2000). Accordingly, tourists' sensory dimensions play an important role in forming their overall experience (Agapito, Mendes and Valle, 2013).

This is consistent with majority findings on the characteristics of millennials, who are said to view travelling as an opportunity to experience a new culture (Cavagnaro and Staffieri, 2015). In this notion, the main reasons for their travelling consumption behaviours is driven by internal needs or intrinsic factors. Millennials travel as they desire to achieve self-fulfilment and emotional needs. Drawing from this, millennials are the appropriate target market for ecotourism sector. Millennials have been said to have stronger desire to participate in social and environmental campaigns (Valentine and Powers, 2013). In practical terms, pro-environmental programs should not be mundane but should be exciting, meaningful yet challenging to create an impact on the millennials' emotions and epistemic values. For example, over 600 scuba divers recently set a world record by being the largest group of divers to simultaneously collect plastic debris from the ocean floor in Florida (Independent News, 2019). Tourists' participation in such conservational programs is able to create an unforgettable emotional and epistemic experience that has an overall positive impact on the environment.

Moreover, results of this study have also confirmed that responsible environmental behaviour is a precursor and also acts as a mediator between personal consumption values and destination choice. In terms of product repurchase, Olsen (2007) proved that customer involvement is an important mediator. Millennial tourists' consumption values result in their destination choice of marine park islands through their involvement in green activities. In an online study conducted on tourists from four English-speaking countries (Australia, United States, United Kingdom and Canada), engagement in voluntary environmental activities was significantly associated to responsible travelling decisions (Juvan and Dolnicar, 2017). Subsequently, park visitors who developed a stronger sense of belongingness had a higher tendency to behave responsibly (Ramkissoon et al., 2013). It is suggested that the marine park's management

should highly encourage visitors to behave responsibly, either through policy enforcement or by organizing consistent eco-friendly programs as part of their ecotourism experience. On-site responsible environmental behavioural items can accurately reflect the behaviours of tourists (Lee et al., 2013). Closer to home, Fuze Ecoteer works closely with the Department of Marine Park and Reef Check Malaysia on the Perhentian Marine Research Center (PMRC) that offers dive courses for volunteers to develop skills in coral management, seagrass watch and overall marine ecosystem monitoring (Ecoteer, 2019). As a result of the amazing experience, positive social media reviews and testimonials were found among the volunteers who immersed themselves in the conservation project at PMRC. They developed stronger bonds to the destination and have indicated that they would most likely to return (Fuze Ecoteer Facebook page, 2019). In a study conducted on young local residents of an island holiday destination in Spain, it was concluded that attachment and familiarity influenced their willingness to travel more in the island and recommend the island to outsiders (Martínez-González et al., 2016). Emphasis should be placed on programs that could embed a pleasurable and memorable travel experience in the marine parks not only among foreign visitors, but also the local tourists to reinforce their revisit choice to the islands. Overall experience have been found to influence word-of-mouth, visit intention and destination loyalty (Fujioka, 2009; Rivera and Croes, 2010; Hosany and Prayag, 2013).

The findings indicate that the tourists' development of consumption values and destination decision are created through their active and voluntary behaviour in various pro-environmental practices. Contradictorily, tourists' active participation of general green behaviours at home does not necessarily mean that they will engage similarly when they are on holiday (Bergin-Seers and Mair, 2009). Thus, it is believed that marketers and marine park authorities should focus on actively involving millennial tourists in pro-environmental activities in the marine park itself to attract the right segment of tourists continuously. This includes boosting their participation in recycling efforts, encouraging waste management and self-regulation towards the park's rules while promoting knowledge-sharing among visitors on non-disruptive behaviours towards the natural flora and fauna. Besides this, park authorities should also consider making other aspects of their visit more environmental-friendly by encouraging accommodation providers to adopt green practices and tour operators to organize more eco-friendly tour packages. The tourists' voluntary behaviours towards the environmental causes in the marine parks itself would enable them to act as the co-producer of their overall travel experience, hence positively influencing their value creation (input) and decisional (output) process.

6. Conclusion and Future Research

Individuals who are born in the millennial generation have been said to differ in terms of their values, behaviours, consumption patterns and preferences (Gardiner et al., 2012). Knowledge on responsible millennial tourists are therefore significant, as they are the generational group that has paved the development of niche or alternative tourism sectors. Based on the results, the present study uncovered that personal consumption values dimension as a formative construct did have a significant but weak influence on tourists' pro-environmental behaviours. Advancing from this, it further confirms the positive influence of pro-environmental behaviours towards millennial tourists' preference for choosing marine park islands as a holiday destination. The finding is relevant as the responsible behaviour of tourists measured is site-specific. This study provides evidence that tourists who partake in conservational activities such as sorting their trash and helping to maintain the natural setting develop a more memorable experience and are inclined to choose an ecotourism destination.

Though the results of this study gathered that personal consumption values have a weak influence on pro-environmental behaviour of millennial tourists, it is evident that other psychosocial and external factors may have bigger impact on their behaviours. For instance, a recent study has confirmed that cultural differences may exist among tourists that could influence their motivations and relationships with the nature (Jiang et al., 2019). Besides, there could exist some form of barriers or perceived risks that may impede their behaviours. It is said that customers face various types of risks such as time, physical limitations and financial risks that creates a negative risk perception (Wang et al., 2013). Conditional values as prescribed in this study may have address this, but it is insufficient to encompass all other possible challenges based on each individual situation. In view of this, it is suggested that future studies may consider conditional value as a moderator variable. Tourists' motivation to behave a certain way is often complicated, multifaceted and influenced by different situational context. Since this study is limited to the millennial visitors in marine park islands only, a comparative study can also be conducted to evaluate the disparity between the millennial tourists' behaviours and decisions in other nature parks such as the national park or wildlife reserve parks. This would provide a broader assessment on the influence of the varied eco-friendly activities in a slightly different setting. Previous studies in the literature reviews have identified that differences of behaviour may exist between travellers from different regions. In view that this study did not distinguish between local and international tourist groups, it would be worthy to examine if their nationality and cultural background would influence their behaviour and choices. Tourism marketing research should shift away from focusing too much on factors that only attract financial growth and tourist numbers but should seek to discover knowledge on niche segments and ways to encourage a more balanced tourism development that cares for the locals and its ecosystem. Essentially, environmentally responsible millennial tourists like to feel personally connected to the ecotourism destination.

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